

C-IMMSIM simulation results

May 7, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.


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15]      pos=1271 len=5      SGPSA
16]      pos=1318 len=5      SSATG
17]      pos=1335 len=8      GAQSGGST
18]      pos=1355 len=14     EREDEDDWDEED
19]      pos=1398 len=22     KSSGGKGGYSQAASSDSAQGS

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DoPeptideList_I:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 4 MHCI molecules

Read class I peptide list from file? NO

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Allele: A0201
Pseudo sequence: KAAHVEQRKAQTRTV
Threshold: 9.523800
Max score: 27.437000

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Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-064240_5_BpeE82RgBRVo.FSA_1_001

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MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHFVRVRMVSPFLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATI AVMSLMGSSRFDPVEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEYML
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWMMRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRLLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAAGLLGTGALLAAALTTLWHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDLTLA
LHVLVTHAVPDAVA AVVAPVGVLVYLVVDWRVALVFGPVLYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLAGKKTMLDLATRPATFLWLIAATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGIAAYGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFVDFVTFGYRPGVPIQDVSLTLRPGVTVA
LVGPSGSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAI RVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHDRVLRRLPDGYDTVLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARA ILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWDWTGQGSRVAVAAAQDGTMSYMIATPAAL TAAATDIDGI
GSAVSVANAAVAATTGVL AAGGDEVLAATARLFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEH
RAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRLRQRHFQCGGQPEFRQHSEHRRMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTL SAA
LDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAA YTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQA
VLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFIRMNQAALAMEVYQAETA VNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNP IFGMPSPGSSTP
VGQLPAAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQTLTQLPQVTSLFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHP LAGGSGPSAGAGL
LRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPV GAGAMGQGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREED
DEDDWDEEDDWIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGGYSQAASSDSAQGS DVS LTA

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Epitopes of protein 0 -----

```

0]      pos= 26 score=0.002404 unnormalised=0.3592000000      SIAPHFVRV
1]      pos= 131 score=0.011675 unnormalised=1.7442000000      LLIGDSASI
2]      pos= 141 score=0.003857 unnormalised=0.5762000000      GMNGIETV
3]      pos= 289 score=0.001835 unnormalised=0.2742000000      KLPLVLSGV
4]      pos= 293 score=0.019326 unnormalised=2.8872000000      VLSGVLAAL
5]      pos= 303 score=0.035478 unnormalised=5.3002000000      TLAQLAPFV
6]      pos= 306 score=0.014092 unnormalised=2.1052000000      QLAPFVLLV
7]      pos= 338 score=0.000162 unnormalised=0.0242000000      GLLGTGALL
8]      pos= 344 score=0.001173 unnormalised=0.1752000000      ALLAAALTL
9]      pos= 407 score=0.006401 unnormalised=0.9562000000      AVPDAVA AV
10]     pos= 411 score=0.015430 unnormalised=2.3052000000      AVAAVVAPV
11]     pos= 424 score=0.023637 unnormalised=3.5312000000      YLFVVDWRV
12]     pos= 495 score=0.006240 unnormalised=0.9322000000      RLDEYIGFL
13]     pos= 502 score=0.007411 unnormalised=1.1072000000      FLVAWQRPL
14]     pos= 561 score=0.011936 unnormalised=1.7832000000      RLLGIAYGL
15]     pos= 576 score=0.007699 unnormalised=1.1502000000      LLAARHLQV

```

16]	pos= 585	score=0.005778	unnormalised=0.8632000000	TLDETELAV
17]	pos= 653	score=0.004259	unnormalised=0.6362000000	TLLARFHDV
18]	pos= 730	score=0.009680	unnormalised=1.4462000000	RLPDGYDTV
19]	pos= 767	score=0.016301	unnormalised=2.4352000000	ILDEATAFA
20]	pos= 861	score=0.030531	unnormalised=4.5612000000	YMIATPAAL
21]	pos= 897	score=0.014955	unnormalised=2.2342000000	VLAAGGDEV
22]	pos=1066	score=0.035532	unnormalised=5.3082000000	ALAAATPMV
23]	pos=1135	score=0.010256	unnormalised=1.5322000000	ALTEMDYFI
24]	pos=1164	score=0.002177	unnormalised=0.3252000000	TLFEKLEPM
25]	pos= -1	score=0.701775	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

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Allele: A0203
Pseudo sequence: KAAHVEQRKKAQTRV
Threshold: 10.639400
Max score: 26.625000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-064240_5_BpeE82RgbRVo.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVMRLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHFVRVVRMVSPTLFDQAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAVMSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEMYL
EQHDDNDTILPLAKHPRLRVRWVRRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALCKVRVRLRDEFKPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKLLVDDTLA
LHYLVTHAVPDAAVAVVAPVGVLVYLFVVDWRVALVLFQPVLYLTTSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRLAGKKTMLMDLATRPATFLWLIATGTLVAVTHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGIAYGLGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGTVTA
LVGPGSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHDRVLRLLPDGYDTVLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARAILGDTPLVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRVTLVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWDTGGSRVAVAAAQDGTMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDGI
GSAVSVANAATAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAARLARNAAEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEH
RAAGAGRRRRRRSGDQWRLRQRHFQCGGQPEFRQHSEHRRMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTLTSA
LDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAYTQAMATPSPLEIAANHITQA
VLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAETAVENTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNPFGMPSPGSSTP
VGQLPAAATQTLGQLEMSGPMQQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHPLAGGSGPSAGAGL
LRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPMLSQLIEKPVAVSMPAAAAAGSSATGGAAPVAGAMGQGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREED
DEDDWDEEDDWIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 26	score=0.007753	unnormalised=1.0016000000	SIAPHFVRV
1]	pos= 131	score=0.017453	unnormalised=2.2546000000	LLIGDSASI
2]	pos= 289	score=0.006530	unnormalised=0.8436000000	KLPLVLSGV
3]	pos= 293	score=0.004363	unnormalised=0.5636000000	VLSGVLAAL
4]	pos= 303	score=0.025318	unnormalised=3.2706000000	TLAQLAPFV
5]	pos= 306	score=0.016114	unnormalised=2.0816000000	QLAPFVLLV
6]	pos= 407	score=0.017020	unnormalised=2.1986000000	AVPDAVAAV
7]	pos= 411	score=0.022345	unnormalised=2.8866000000	AVAAVVAPV
8]	pos= 576	score=0.004943	unnormalised=0.6386000000	LLAARHLQV
9]	pos= 730	score=0.007645	unnormalised=0.9876000000	RLPDGYDTV
10]	pos= 861	score=0.022253	unnormalised=2.8746000000	YMIATPAAL
11]	pos=1007	score=0.005036	unnormalised=0.6506000000	AMPPELNTA
12]	pos=1066	score=0.031642	unnormalised=4.0876000000	ALAAATPMV
13]	pos= -1	score=0.811583	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

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Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-064240_5_BpeE82RgbrVo.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVM LRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHFVRVRMVSPFLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATTAVMSLMGSSRFVDVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEYML
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRVWMMRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRL LAPKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFAAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDTLA
LHVLVTHAVPDAVA AVVAVPVGLVYLVFVVDWRVALVLFPGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMGNEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLAGKKTLMDLATRPATFLWLI AATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGAIYGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFHDVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGTVTA
LVGPSGSKSTL ATLLARFHDVERGAI RVEGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLEQAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHQHRLRRLPDGYDTVLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARA ILGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWDGTGQSRVAVAAAQDGTMSYMIATPAAL TAAATDIDGI
GSAVSVANAAVAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAATARLFNANAEEYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTL TGGCGVFRRRRRGRQCVTAAEH
RAAGARRRRRRSGDGQWRLRQRHFQCGGQPEFRQHSEHRRMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGAPMLAAAAGWQTL SAA
LDAQVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQA
VLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAETA VNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNP IFGMPSGSSSTP
VGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQTLTQLPQQVTSLSFQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHP LAGGSGPSAGAGL
LRAESLPGAGGSLTRPTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPV GAGAMGQGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREED
DEDDWDEEDDWIVIGVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGS DVS LTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 0	score=0.006274	unnormalised=1.1752000000	MARGLQGMV
1]	pos= 28	score=0.017404	unnormalised=3.2602000000	APHFVRVRM
2]	pos= 33	score=0.005142	unnormalised=0.9632000000	RVRMVSPTL
3]	pos= 77	score=0.007154	unnormalised=1.3402000000	DPAAGRFAV
4]	pos= 104	score=0.006834	unnormalised=1.2802000000	KPGATTIADM
5]	pos= 169	score=0.009968	unnormalised=1.8672000000	IPLAKHPRL
6]	pos= 174	score=0.028086	unnormalised=5.2612000000	HPRLRVRVW
7]	pos= 268	score=0.028406	unnormalised=5.3212000000	VPAPARGSW
8]	pos= 270	score=0.007379	unnormalised=1.3822000000	APARGSWRA
9]	pos= 286	score=0.018536	unnormalised=3.4722000000	APLKLPLVL
10]	pos= 290	score=0.017217	unnormalised=3.2252000000	LPLVLSGVL
11]	pos= 308	score=0.007811	unnormalised=1.4632000000	APFVLLVEL
12]	pos= 361	score=0.004266	unnormalised=0.7992000000	FARALRLRL
13]	pos= 417	score=0.002729	unnormalised=0.5112000000	APVGVLVYL
14]	pos= 508	score=0.030035	unnormalised=5.6262000000	RPLAGKKTLL
15]	pos= 522	score=0.007064	unnormalised=1.3232000000	RPATFLWLI
16]	pos= 578	score=0.010704	unnormalised=2.0052000000	AARHLQVTL
17]	pos= 622	score=0.004779	unnormalised=0.8952000000	VPVIQDVSL
18]	pos= 633	score=0.009226	unnormalised=1.7282000000	RPGTVTALV
19]	pos= 642	score=0.003701	unnormalised=0.6932000000	GPSGSGKST
20]	pos= 710	score=0.012685	unnormalised=2.3762000000	APAEQVQVA
21]	pos= 865	score=0.035901	unnormalised=6.7252000000	TPAAL TAAA
22]	pos=1022	score=0.016443	unnormalised=3.0802000000	GPAPMLAAA
23]	pos=1024	score=0.004314	unnormalised=0.8082000000	APMLAAAAG
24]	pos=1105	score=0.007811	unnormalised=1.4632000000	TPSLPEIAA
25]	pos=1191	score=0.013416	unnormalised=2.5132000000	MPSPGSSSTP
26]	pos=1198	score=0.009311	unnormalised=1.7442000000	TPVQQLPPA
27]	pos=1203	score=0.035672	unnormalised=6.6822000000	LPPAATQTL
28]	pos=1226	score=0.011719	unnormalised=2.1952000000	QPLQQVTSLL
29]	pos=1272	score=0.018264	unnormalised=3.4212000000	GPSAGAGLL
30]	pos=1307	score=0.020954	unnormalised=3.9252000000	APSVMPAAA
31]	pos=1311	score=0.021120	unnormalised=3.9562000000	MPAAAAGSS
32]	pos= -1	score=0.559676	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

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Allele: B5301
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQIKTQTRE
Threshold: 8.175800
Max score: 25.226000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-064240_5_BpeE82RgBRVo.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAIPHFRVVRMVSPTLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDPNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVAVDVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATIAVMSLMGSSRFVPEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIETVPNDVPIEYML
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVRRRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRLLAPLKLPLVLSGVLAAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFAAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLLSKLSRPLGWFTSRGSGSIIKKLVDDTLA
LHYLVTHAVPDAVAAVVAPVGVLVYLVFVVDWRVALVLFPGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSSFRRLDEYIGFLVAVQRPLAGKKTLMDLATRPATFLWLIAATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGIAYLGGRLTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLTLRPGTVTA
LVGPSGSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAIIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAQIHDRVLRPLPDGYDVTLVGANSGLSGGERQLTIARAILGDTPVLILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCRWLWDTGQGSRVAVAAAQDGTMSYMIATPAALTAATDIDGI
GSAVSVANAAAAATTGVLAAGGDEVLAARIARLFNANAEEYHALSAQVAFAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEH
RAAGAGRRQRRRRSGDQWRLRQRHFQCGGQPEFRQHSEHRRMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTLSSAA
LDAQAVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQTASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQA
VLATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFYIRMNQAALAMEVYQAETAVENTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNPFGMPSPGSSTP
VGLPQAATQTLQQLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLSFQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPNSHPLAGGSGPSAGAGL
LRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSSATGGAAPVAGAMGQAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREED
DEDDWDEEDWIVGIVAGLAVLAVVIGAVVATVMCRKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGSDVSLTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 23	score=0.016215	unnormalised=2.6242000000	ETISIAPHF
1]	pos= 44	score=0.009363	unnormalised=1.5152000000	DAEAEPAAW
2]	pos= 48	score=0.034920	unnormalised=5.6512000000	EPAAWLRFW
3]	pos= 59	score=0.036143	unnormalised=5.8492000000	DPNGSNTEF
4]	pos= 75	score=0.008411	unnormalised=1.3612000000	EADPAAGRF
5]	pos= 77	score=0.004697	unnormalised=0.7602000000	DPAAGRFV
6]	pos= 91	score=0.054508	unnormalised=8.8212000000	DPAGPASSW
7]	pos= 112	score=0.006489	unnormalised=1.0502000000	MSLMGSSRF
8]	pos= 122	score=0.012835	unnormalised=2.0772000000	VPEEQPAGY
9]	pos= 149	score=0.012977	unnormalised=2.1002000000	VPNDVPIEM
10]	pos= 205	score=0.005216	unnormalised=0.8442000000	WATPEAAAL
11]	pos= 250	score=0.011420	unnormalised=1.8482000000	EPAATEPEV
12]	pos= 268	score=0.028623	unnormalised=4.6322000000	VPAPARGSW
13]	pos= 290	score=0.003221	unnormalised=0.5212000000	LPLVLSGVL
14]	pos= 522	score=0.007979	unnormalised=1.2912000000	RPATFLWLI
15]	pos= 544	score=0.018916	unnormalised=3.0612000000	DPVNLLPFM
16]	pos= 622	score=0.007144	unnormalised=1.1562000000	VPVIQDVSL
17]	pos= 731	score=0.009733	unnormalised=1.5752000000	LPDGYDVTL
18]	pos=1018	score=0.004592	unnormalised=0.7432000000	MAGAGPAPM
19]	pos=1090	score=0.018934	unnormalised=3.0642000000	QATAQAAAY
20]	pos=1094	score=0.004747	unnormalised=0.7682000000	QAAAAYTQAM
21]	pos=1100	score=0.002090	unnormalised=0.3382000000	QAMATTPSL
22]	pos=1108	score=0.008516	unnormalised=1.3782000000	LPEIAANHI
23]	pos=1118	score=0.005575	unnormalised=0.9022000000	QAVLTATNF
24]	pos=1203	score=0.014189	unnormalised=2.2962000000	LPPAATQTL
25]	pos=1226	score=0.004716	unnormalised=0.7632000000	QPLQVTSLS
26]	pos= -1	score=0.647830	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

DoPeptideList_II:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

Allele: DRB3_0101
Pseudo sequence: RVTLGRDAYW
Threshold: 2.631130
Max score: 27.850000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-064240_5_BpeE82RgbrVo.FSA_1_001

MARGLQGVMLRSFGARDHTATVIETISIAPIHFVRVRMVSPFLFQDAEAEPAAWLRFWFPDNGSNTEFQRAYTISEADPA
AGRFVADVVLHDPAGPASSWARTVKPGATI AVMSLMGSSRFDPVEEQPAGYLLIGDSASIPGMNGIIETVPNDVPIEMYL
EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWVRRDEKSLAEIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFQPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRL LAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIIKLVTDTLA
LHVLVTHAVPDAVA AVVAVPVGVLVYLVFVVDWRVALVLFVGPVLYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNGEAGSYLEGQ
PVIRVFGAASSSFRRLDEYIGFLVAWQRPLAGKKTMLDLATRPATFLWLIATGTLVATHRMDPVNLLPFMFLGTTFG
ARLLGAIYGLGGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELA VREHPREPLDGEAPATVVDHVTFGYRPGVPIQDVS LTLRPGTVTA
LVGPSGSGKSTLALLARFHDVERGAI RGVGGDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIQHDRVLRLLPDGYDVTLVGANSGLSGGERQLTIARA LIGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
AHLRHTITRADQIVVLDHGRIVERGTHEELLAAGGRYCR LWDTGQGSRVAVAAAQDGTMSYMIATPAAL TAAATDIDGI
GSAVSVANAAAVATTGVL AAGGDEVLAATARLFNANA EYHALSAQVAAFQTLFVRTLTGGCGVFRRRRGRQCVTAAEH
RAAGAGRRRQRRRSGDGQWRQRQRFHFCGGQPEFRQHSEHRRMLWHAMPPELNTARLMAGAGPAPMLAAAAGWQTL SAA
LDAQVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSDKALAAATPMVVWLQ TASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAAAYTQAMATPSLPEIAANHITQA
VLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFIRMNWQAALAMEVYQAE TAVNTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNP IFGMPSPGSSTP
VGQLPPAATQTLGQLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLSFSQV GGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHP LAGGSGPSAGACL
LRAESLPGAGGSLTRTPLMSQLIEKPVAPSVMPAAAAGSS ATGGAAPV GAGAMGQGAQSGGSTRPGLVAPAPLAQEREED
DEDDWDEEDDWIVGIVAGLAVLAVVVIGAVVATVMCR RKSSGGKGSYSQAASSDSAQGS DVS LTA

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

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4]	pos= 88	score=0.026311	unnormalised=6.5108700000	VLHDPAGPA
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6]	pos= 132	score=0.016026	unnormalised=3.9658700000	LIGDSASIP
7]	pos= 145	score=0.017081	unnormalised=4.2268700000	IIETVPNDV
8]	pos= 160	score=0.005269	unnormalised=1.3038700000	EQHDDNDTL
9]	pos= 161	score=0.004372	unnormalised=1.0818700000	QHDDNDTLI
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11]	pos= 195	score=0.008029	unnormalised=1.9868700000	ENRDWSDWY
12]	pos= 312	score=0.028905	unnormalised=7.1528700000	LLVELSRL
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15]	pos= 393	score=0.005831	unnormalised=1.4428700000	VTDLTLALH
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17]	pos= 407	score=0.002792	unnormalised=0.6908700000	AVPDAVA AV
18]	pos= 426	score=0.037525	unnormalised=9.2858700000	FVVDWRVAL
19]	pos= 442	score=0.001232	unnormalised=0.3048700000	VYLTITSSL
20]	pos= 444	score=0.007629	unnormalised=1.8878700000	LTITSSLT I
21]	pos= 446	score=0.010809	unnormalised=2.6748700000	ITSSLT IQS
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23]	pos= 485	score=0.005301	unnormalised=1.3118700000	FGAASSSFR
24]	pos= 494	score=0.001858	unnormalised=0.4598700000	RRLDEYIGF
25]	pos= 502	score=0.001470	unnormalised=0.3638700000	FLVAWQRPL
26]	pos= 541	score=0.048629	unnormalised=12.0338700000	HRMDPVNLL
27]	pos= 584	score=0.033007	unnormalised=8.1678700000	VTLDETELA
28]	pos= 616	score=0.000929	unnormalised=0.2298700000	FGYRPGV PV
29]	pos= 624	score=0.037820	unnormalised=9.3588700000	VIQDVS LTL
30]	pos= 676	score=0.004764	unnormalised=1.1788700000	LAADELYTR
31]	pos= 687	score=0.029645	unnormalised=7.3358700000	FVLQEAQLV
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33]	pos= 759	score=0.056352	unnormalised=13.9448700000	ILGDTPVL
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35]	pos= 773	score=0.011177	unnormalised=2.7658700000	AFADPESEY
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48]	pos= -1	score=0.267388	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event

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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/27330_20250507-064240_5_BpeE82RgBRVo.FSA_1_001

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EQHDDNDTLIPLAKHPRLRVRWMMRDEKSLAEAIENRDWSDWYAWATPEAAALKCVRVRLRDEFGFPKSEIHAQAYWNA
GRAMGTHRATEPAATEPEVGAAPQPESAVPAPARGSWRAQAASRL LAPLKLPLVLSGVLAALVTLAQLAPFVLLVELSRL
LVSGAGAHRLFTVGFVAVGLLGTGALLAAALTLWLHVIDARFARALRLRLSKLSRLPLGWFTSRGSGSIKKLVTDTLA
LHVLVTHAVPDAVAVVAVPVGLVYLVFVVDWRVALVFGPVLVYLTITSSLTIQSGPRIVQAQRWAEKMNAGEAGSYLEGQ
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ARLLGIA YGLGLRTGLLAARHLQVTLDETELAVREHPREPLDGEAPATVVFVDFVTFGYRPGVPVIQDVSLLRPGTVTA
LVGPSGSGKSTL ATLLARFHDVERGARIRVGGQDIRSLAADELYTRVGFVLQEAQLVHGTAENIALAVPDAPAEQVQVAA
REAIHQDRVRLRDPGYDVTLGANSGLSGGERQLTIARA I LGDTPVILDEATAFADPESEYLVQALNRLTRDRTVLVI
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LDAQVELTARLNSLGEAWTGGGSKLAAATPMVVVLQ TASTQAKTRAMQATAQAAA YTQAMATTPSLPEIAANHITQA
VLTATNFFGINTIPIALTEMDFYFIRMWNQAALAMEVYQAETAVENTLFEKLEPMASILDPGASQSTTNP IFGMPSPGSSTP
VGQLPPAATQTLQQLGEMSGPMQLTQPLQVTSLSFQVGGTGGGNPADEEAAQMGLLGTSPLSNHPLAGGSGPSAGAGL
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Epitopes of protein 0 -----

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5]	pos= 112	score=0.013043	unnormalised=7.6225600000	MSLMGSSRF
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